

Autonomic involvement in Parkinsonian carriers of PARK2 gene mutations

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Abstract

Background and objectives: The objective of this study was to assess the presence of autonomic nervous system dysfunction in PARK2 mutation carriers.

Patients and methods: We performed a cross-sectional analysis of 8 PARK2 carriers (age: 60.1 ± 12.8 years) and 13 individuals with idiopathic PD (iPD) (age: 59.2 ± 8.9 years). Autonomic dysfunction was measured using the SCOPA-AUT questionnaire, non-invasive autonomic tests and responses of noradrenaline and vasopressin levels to postural changes. Myocardial sympathetic denervation was assessed with metaiodobenzylguanidine (MIBG) scintigraphy. This damage was further investigated in postmortem epicardial tissue of one PARK2 carrier and three control cases (two PD patients and one subject without PD).

Results: The prevalence of autonomic symptoms and orthostatic hypotension (OH) was lower in PARK2 mutation carriers than in iPD patients (SCOPA OUT: 3.4 ± 4.8 vs. 14.7 ± 7.2 , $p < 0.001$; OH: present in three iPD patients but none of the PARK2 mutation carriers). Second, sympathetic myocardial denervation was less severe in PARK2 mutation carriers compared to controls, both in MIBG scintigraphy (late H/ M uptake ratio: 1.52 ± 0.35 vs. 1.32 ± 0.25 $p < 0.05$) and in postmortem tissue study. Interestingly, axonal alpha-synuclein deposits were absent in epicardial tissue of the PARK2 mutation carrier while they were present in the two PD patients.

Interpretation: Our study supports the view that autonomic nervous system dysfunction and myocardial sympathetic denervation are less pronounced in PARK2 mutation carriers than in individuals with iPD, suggesting that the involvement of small peripheral sympathetic nerve fibers is a minor pathological hallmark in PARK2 carriers

Keywords: Parkinson's disease Autonomic function PARK2 mutation Autonomic tests

1. Introduction

Mutations in the PARK2 gene explain up to half of the cases with recessively inherited Parkinson's disease (PD), and 15% of sporadic PD with onset before 45 years of age [1]. Compared to idiopathic PD (iPD), patients with PARK2 gene mutations have significantly earlier and more symmetrical onset, more frequent dystonia, slower progression, and a tendency toward a greater response to low doses of levodopa with early fluctuations and dyskinesia [2]. Heterozygous PARK2 mutations are relatively frequent and it has been speculated that they are associated with PD [3]. The majority of PD patients with mutations in the PARK2 gene do not exhibit the classical neuropathological markers of PD; however, in a few cases, pathological analysis of PARK2 mutation carriers has revealed Lewy bodies in the substantia nigra and locus coeruleus, and alpha-synuclein immunopositive inclusion bodies in the brain [4e7].

Autonomic nervous system involvement in PARK2 mutation is a matter of discussion. In early reports, it was observed that patients with PARK2 mutations showed some autonomic symptoms resembling those observed in PD [8,9]. However, recent studies have shown that cardiovascular dysautonomia is not associated with the PARK2 phenotype [10,11]. In addition, a few case reports in PARK2-positive PD patients have noted normal 123I-MIBG scans [12,13,8] and preserved TH-immunoreactive fibers in the epicardium [12]. While these findings support the view that small myelinated and unmyelinated autonomic nerve fibers are preserved in PARK2 mutation carriers, this hypothesis contrasts with the presence of parkin protein in the axoplasm of bovine myelinated nerve fibers and Schwann cells [14] and with the presence of peripheral neuropathy in PARK2 mutation carriers [15]. The main objective of this study was to assess the overall level of autonomic nervous system dysfunction and the specific involvement of the neurocirculatory system, including myocardial sympathetic denervation, in 8 PARK2 mutation carriers compared to 13 iPD patients. We performed a comprehensive assessment of autonomic symptoms, quantified hemodynamic dysfunction by noninvasive tests and plasma neurohormone levels, and carried out myocardial MIBG scintigraphy in all patients. In addition, we assessed epicardial denervation in the postmortem tissue from one PARK2 mutation carrier,

two patients with PD (one with iPD and one symptomatic alpha synuclein mutation carrier) and one subject without PD.

2. Patients and Methods

2.1 Study population

We included 8 PARK2 gene mutation carriers (60.1 ± 12.8 years; with a disease duration of 27.1 ± 11.4 years; 4 men) and 13 control patients with iPD (age: 59.2 ± 8.9 years, with a disease duration of 6.5 ± 5.1 years; 8 men). Patients classified as idiopathic had no family history of PD. All participants fulfilled the UK Parkinson's disease Society Brain Bank criteria for the clinical diagnosis of PD (except for family history of PD in PARK2 carriers). They were consecutively recruited in the Movement Disorders and Autonomic Unit at Cruces University Hospital. We excluded patients with diabetes or with myocardial perfusion defects observed in the ^{99m}Tc -MIBI SPECT, and any patients who were not able to complete the tests properly due to physical or cognitive disability. We also excluded one patient with one heterozygous PARK2 mutation and another with a heterozygous compound PARK2 mutation that developed parkinsonian symptoms when exposed to clebopride, which resolved when the drug was discontinued. All procedures were carried out with the adequate understanding and written consent of the patients involved, and with the approval of the local ethics committee.

2.2 Clinical assessment of PD

At study inclusion, we collected a set of clinical and demographic data including gender, age, disease duration, age at disease onset and scores on the Unified Parkinson Disease Rating Scale (UPDRS I-IV) and the 12-item Brief Identification Smell Test (BSIT; Sensonic®). We classified the BSIT result as normal or abnormal following the norms for age and gender provided by the manufacturer.

2.3 Molecular genetic analysis

PARK2 mutations were identified on DNA obtained from peripheral lymphocytes. Single-strand conformation polymorphism (SSCP) analysis of the 12 exons was followed

by nucleotide sequencing whenever an SSCP band shift was observed. To detect alterations in gene dosage (deletions and duplications), a quantitative RTPCR assay was performed [10].

2.4 Study of the autonomic nervous system

Assessments were made early in the morning, after 12 h of fasting and overnight bed rest. Participants were not allowed to consume drugs or foods capable of modifying blood catecholamine levels within the previous 24 h. For the analysis of noradrenaline (NA) and vasopressin levels, peripheral blood samples were collected (30 ml from arm venipuncture) after the patient had rested for at least 40 min in the supine position, and again after standing for 3 min. NA levels were measured by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with electrochemical detection, while plasma vasopressin was measured by radioimmunoassay (RIA).

We then analyzed heart rate and blood pressure variability during various physical maneuvers using a continuous monitoring device, the Task Force® Monitor (CNSystems, Graz, Austria): a 20-min tilt table test (TTT) at an inclination of 60°; the Valsalva maneuver (VM) (40 mmHg for at least 15 s); isometric contraction (handgrip isometer); and deep breathing (6 inspiration/expiration cycles) (I/E). Finally, we administered the SCOPA-AUT, a brief questionnaire concerning autonomic symptoms classified into 6 dimensions [16].

2.5 Myocardial MIBG scintigraphy

All participants underwent myocardial MIBG scintigraphy with a gamma camera no more than 6 months before study inclusion. We analyzed the early (15 min) and late (4 h) heart-to-mediastinum uptake ratios. Participants also underwent 99mTc-MIBI (6-methoxy isobutyl isonitrile) SPECT to rule out myocardial perfusion defects.

2.6 Postmortem histopathological studies of epicardial and brain tissues

In order to further characterize epicardial sympathetic nerve involvement in PARK2 carriers, we performed immunohistochemical analysis of postmortem myocardial and epicardial tissue from one PARK2 mutation carrier. Brain tissue from this patient was also

studied to evaluate the presence of Lewy Body pathology. As a reference, we studied post mortem epicardial and brain samples from one subject without PD and from two PD patients: one iPD patient (with no family history of PD) and another PD patient with a specific mutation (E46K) in the alpha synuclein gene (SNCA), a condition associated with an aggressively progressing Lewy Body disease, with marked autonomic dysfunction and cardiac denervation. Epicardial samples were sliced into 5-mm-thick sections, which were then deparaffinized and subjected to routine histological staining (hematoxylin-eosin) and standard immunohistochemical processing with monoclonal antibodies against neurofilaments (NF), tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) (TH16; Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA) (1:3000), phosphorylated alpha synuclein and alpha synuclein (Zymed®). Regarding brain samples, blocks were taken from representative cortical and subcortical regions in accordance with standardized protocols. The paraffin-embedded sections were stained with routine histological methods and processed for immunocytochemistry with antibodies against glial fibrillary acidic protein (1:5000; Dako, Carpinteria, CA), phosphorylated NF (1:40, Zymed, San Francisco, CA), tau (1:400; Sigma, St. Louis, MO), ubiquitin (Z0458, 1:400; Dako), and alpha synuclein (1:200, without formic acid pretreatment; Zymed).

2.7 Statistical analysis

Descriptive data were expressed using the mean and standard deviation for the quantitative variables, and percentages for the qualitative variables. The Mann-Whitney U non-parametric test was used to compare mean ranks. All the analyses were carried out with the statistical software package SPSS 13 for Windows (SPSS, Chicago, IL).

3. Results

Table 1 shows an individual description of the main characteristics of the 8 PARK2 mutation carriers in terms of demographics, family history, genetics and duration of PD, as well as a summary of the main outcomes from autonomic nervous system and myocardial SPECT MIBG assessments. Of these patients, three carried homozygous and five compound heterozygous mutations; and, while two had no family history of PD, the

remaining six mutations occurred in three sibling sets, one of which was the product of a consanguineous marriage.

There were no statistically significant differences between PARK2 mutation carriers and iPD patients in terms of age or motor status (UPDRS III scale) at inclusion. Disease onset was before the age of 50 years in all PARK2 mutation carriers and occurred significantly earlier than in individuals with iPD. Consequently, disease duration was longer in PARK2 mutation carriers (27.1 ± 13.4 years in PARK2 mutation carriers vs. 6.5 ± 5.1 years in iPD patients; $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

We found a lower prevalence of autonomic symptoms among patients with PARK2 gene mutations based on the SCOPA-AUT score (3.4 ± 4.8 in PARK2 mutation carriers vs. 14.7 ± 7.2 in iPD patients; $p < 0.001$). According to the Ewing and Clarke classification of autonomic failure [17], no PARK2 mutation carriers had definite autonomic failure (6 normal, 2 early) (Table 1). PARK2 mutation carriers had significantly lower scores than iPD patients for most regions and items, especially for digestive, urinary, thermoregulatory and sexual regions. The olfactory system was less affected in PARK2 mutation carriers (BSIT: 7.8 ± 3.2 in PARK2 mutation carriers vs. 6.0 ± 2.6 in iPD patients; $p < 0.05$) (Table 2). Orthostatic hypotension was detected in three patients with iPD, compared to none of PARK2 mutation carriers. However, quantitative assessment of sympathetic function did not reveal differences between PARK2 mutation carriers and individuals with iPD for blood pressure variations during head-up tilt test. No difference between the groups was found in blood pressure response during either late phase II or phase IV of the Valsalva maneuver or in the increase of diastolic blood pressure during isometric hand grip. Cardiovagal function assessment revealed no difference between PARK2 mutation carriers and iPD patients in mean heart rate response during deep breathing (Table 3). On the other hand, we found no significant differences between these groups when comparing the levels of NA response to the head-up tilt test. However, basal and upright values for vasopressin in the PARK2 mutation group were higher than those in iPD patients (Table 3). Lastly, regarding the results on heart imaging by MIBG scintigraphy, we observed that there was less sympathetic denervation in PARK2 mutation carriers than in iPD patients (late H/M uptake ratio: 1.52 ± 0.35 in PARK2 mutation carriers vs. 1.32 ± 0.25 in iPD patients; $p < 0.05$).

We performed a comparative postmortem histopathological study of the brain and heart of one patient carrying a PARK2 gene mutation, one subject without PD who died at age of 60 years from liver disease and two PD patients (Fig. 1). The first PD patient was a 69-year-old man with disease duration of 8 years who was a SNCA mutation carrier (E46K) [18]. The second patient was a 70-year-old woman with PD and no family history of PD who died 9 years after the clinical onset of the disease. The PARK2 mutation carrier was a woman who noted the onset of rest tremor at 43 years of age. She died at the age of 73 and the clinical evaluation months before death revealed advanced motor symptoms, dyskinesia, motor fluctuations and impaired activities of daily living (UPDRS I: 5, UPDRS II: 35, UPDRS III: 66, UPDRS IV: 7). Her brain MRI was unremarkable. A compound heterozygous mutation (C154delA in exon 2 and exon 1 del) in the PARK2 gene was identified in that patient and in two of her relatives: one asymptomatic sister and one brother. Although the autonomic study was not performed in the carrier who underwent an autopsy, it was completed in her brother, who had early onset PD and the same genotype.

The immunohistological analysis of epicardial tissue in the iPD patient and in the SNCA mutation carrier showed a clear Lewy body pathology with an absence of TH-immunoreactive fibers. By contrast, in the PARK2 mutation carrier and in the subject without PD there was only a moderate reduction of TH-immunoreactive fibers and that there were no alpha synuclein inclusions (Fig. 1).

Histology of the brain of the PARK2 mutation carrier showed severe nigral cell degeneration without Lewy body inclusions. Examination of the locus coeruleus found neuron loss without alpha synuclein inclusions. Other brainstem structures such as the inferior olive and noradrenergic nuclei in the pons-medulla and dentate nucleus of the cerebellum showed no significant histological abnormalities. No tau or alpha synuclein inclusions were found in other brain structures, and insignificant levels of (1e42) amyloid Beta A4 (Ab4) were detected in the immunoassay. In contrast, abundant Lewy bodies were observed in the substantia nigra, basal nucleus of Meynert, perifornical area, medullary and pontine tegmentum, periaqueductal gray matter, raphe nuclei, locus coeruleus, area postrema, dorsal motor nuclei of the tenth nerve and frontal cortex of the patient with a SNCA gene mutation. In the case of the iPD patient, numerous alpha synuclein inclusions (LB and Lewy neurites) were found in brainstem nuclei and the substantia nigra. Cortical

involvement was confined to the temporal mesocortex and allocortex-CA2 (Braak III-IV). However, no such inclusions were found in the neocortex, despite the time interval of 9 years from disease onset to death. No Lewy bodies or other alpha synuclein deposits were found in the brain of the subject without PD.

4. Discussion

We report here the first comprehensive study of dysautonomia in patients with mutations in the PARK2 gene and we also provide evidence supporting the idea that PARK2 mutation carriers have less autonomic nervous system involvement than iPD patients. Specifically, in our study PARK2 mutation carriers had fewer autonomic symptoms (SCOPA-AUT scale), less orthostatic hypotension (TTT) and a lower degree of myocardial sympathetic denervation (higher uptake ratios in MIBG scintigraphy). In fact, in PARK2 mutation carriers, the delayed H/M ratios were within the range of patients without PD despite having disease durations of more than 20 years. This idea was further supported by the heart histopathology of one PARK2 mutation carrier, which revealed a relative preservation of epicardial sympathetic fibers, compared with the marked epicardial denervation found in a SNCA mutation carrier and a subject with iPD.

To date, autonomic nervous system involvement has been systematically investigated only in few clinical cohorts of PARK2 mutation carriers. Although initial reports did not mention the presence of autonomic dysfunction in PARK2 mutation carriers with the exception of urinary urgency [2,19], later studies have suggested that several symptoms related to dysautonomia, particularly genitourinary dysfunction, may occur in as many as 60% of PARK2 mutation carriers [8,11,20]. In our study, we found a lower rate of autonomic symptoms using SCOPA-AUT. Specifically, scores were lower in the group of patients with PARK2 gene mutations than in those with iPD for four regions (gastrointestinal, seven items; urinary, six items; thermoregulatory, four items; and sexual, two items for men and two for women).

Orthostatic hypotension on TTT was more common in individuals with iPD than in PARK2 mutation carriers. This finding did not correlate with either clinical symptoms during TTT or cardiovascular symptoms on SCOPA-AUT. The remaining quantitative tests

for cardiovascular reflexes revealed no differences between PARK2 mutation carriers and iPD patients, both in sympathetic and parasympathetic functions [21]. The late H/M ratio of MIBG was less affected in the PARK2 mutation carriers than iPD patients. Similar findings have been previously reported by Orimo et al. [12,13], supporting the view that cardiac sympathetic innervation is well preserved in PARK2 mutation carriers. Our results showing the preservation of TH staining in the epicardic nerve terminals of the PARK2 mutation carrier also support this view.

In line with the present results in PARK2 mutation carriers, our group found similar late H/M ratios of MIBG in symptomatic carriers of the LRRK2 mutations with PD [22]. In contrast, for SNCA gene mutation carriers, myocardial sympathetic innervation ratios have been found to be abnormal from very early stages [18,23]. All these data suggest that normal cardiac uptake of MIBG might be of potential diagnostic value to indicate the absence of Lewy body pathology [12,13] in Parkinsonism.

Histology of the brain in PARK2 mutation carrier showed severe nigral cell loss without Lewy body inclusions. This is in agreement with most of the previously reported PARK2 cases [11,24], with the exception of a few cases in which Lewy bodies were observed in the brain [4e7]. One of the latter cases showed normal uptake of 123I-MIBG scintigraphy and relatively preserved sympathetic nerve fibers in pathological examination of the epicardium, however Lewy body formation was found in the epicardial nerve fibers [5]. To date, there are no definitive explanations to justify the presence of Lewy body inclusions in the brain of some PARK2 mutation carriers. While an older age of onset may well explain the presence of brain Lewy bodies in these subjects, the coexistence of sporadic PD process together with the PARK2 mutation cannot be excluded. It is well known that about 15% of autopsied elderly subjects who had antemortem clinical evaluations ruling out PD or dementia have incidental Lewy bodies (iLBD) in the brain; therefore, the presence of Lewy bodies in the brain of some PARK2 mutation carriers can be also incidental. Other possible explanation would be that in some family pedigrees some other crucial PD susceptibility factors are present [25], like hemizygous deletion [7] or heterozygous PARK2 mutations [4].

Our findings support that the pattern of involvement of peripheral nervous system in PARK2 mutation carriers is different from that observed in iPD and in SNCA-mutation

linked PD. First, our study points that autonomic small myelinated and unmyelinated fibers are relatively well preserved in PARK2 mutation carriers compared to iPD and E46K mutation patients. Second, previous clinical studies in PARK2 carriers have reported a specific damage of large diameter nerve fibers, including peripheral neuropathy in two siblings with PARK2 mutation [15] and a diminished amplitude of sural sensory nerve action potential in nine PARK2 carriers [26]. Moreover, a study by Hase et al. in bovine peripheral nerves demonstrated the presence of parkin protein in the axoplasm and in Schwann cells of large diameter myelinated nerve fibers [14], supporting that parkin plays different roles in the normal physiology of the nervous system, not only in CNS but also in peripheral nervous system. The reason why the sensory nerves are predominantly involved in PARK2 mutation is unclear. A recent multicenter study showed that the duration of exposure to levodopa, along with age, is the main risk factor for the development of neuropathy in iPD [27].

Another relevant finding supporting the presence of sensory neuropathy in PARK2 patients of our study is the significant increase of AVP both in supine and standing positions in PARK2 mutation carriers compared to controls. Previous studies have suggested that the response of arginine-vasopressin (AVP) levels to baroreceptor activation (tilt testing) may be useful to study sensory afferent pathways [28]. In fact, some studies showed that hypotension induced by an upright position produced a slight increase in AVP levels in patients with sensory neuropathies in comparison with normal subjects [29].

The main weakness of our study is the small size of the sample (8 patients with PARK2 gene mutations and 13 iPD patients). Another limitation is the difference in levodopa equivalent doses between the two groups. The PARK2 mutation carriers were treated with a lower LD equivalent dose than the iPD patients, despite having a longer duration of treatment, a fact that may have favored a lower presence of autonomic symptoms in PARK2 carriers. However, we believe that the homogeneity of the sample in terms of age and motor status (Table 2) strengthens the validity of the study.

In conclusion, our study supports the view that the autonomic nervous system is better preserved in patients with mutations in the PARK2 gene than iPD patients, since in most PARK2 mutation carriers there is no involvement of small peripheral sympathetic nerve fibers. In this genetic disorder, the damage of large somatic myelinated nerve fibers is

more severe than in iPD [15,26]. We could speculate that dysautonomia and damage to unmyelinated axons in parkinsonism is related to alpha synuclein pathology, as could be seen in iPD patients [30] and in SNCA mutation carriers, whereas in PARK2 mutation carriers the involvement of myelinated large diameter axons might be more prominent due to the presence of a different pathogenic mechanism to that causing alpha synucleinopathies, for example the loss of function of an abnormal parkin protein.

5. References

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6. Figures

Fig. 1. Immunohistochemical findings of postmortem heart tissue with epicardial nerve fibers from a subject without PD (a, e, i), an iPD patient (b, f, j), a PARK2 mutation carrier (c, g, k) and a SNCA (p.E46K) mutation carrier (d, h, l). Staining for neurofilament (NF) (aed), tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) (eeh) and phosphorylated alpha-synuclein (iem) in 20-mm (a, b, e, f, i, j) and 100-mm (c, d, g, h, k, l) post-fixed sections, cut from paraffin blocks of cardiac tissue. In the subject without PD, we observe slight NF+ and TH+ fibers loss (a, e) and no Lewy bodies or Lewy neurites (i). In the iPD patient, the number of TH-immunoreactive nerve fibers is markedly decreased (b, f) and Lewy bodies (arrow in j) are observed. In the PARK2 mutation carrier slight degeneration of nerve fibers is observed (c, g), with no Lewy body pathology (k). In the SNCA mutation carrier, severe degeneration of nerve fibers (d, h) can be noted with Lewy body pathology (arrows in l, zoom in m).

7. Tables

Table 1: Individualized description of all patients with mutations in the PARK2 gene.

	Case#1	Case#2	Case#3	Case#4	Case#5	Case#6	Case#7	Case#8
Age (years)	71	70	61	65	62	44	71	37
Gender	Female	Female	Male	Female	Female	Male	Male	Male
Type of <i>PARK2</i> mutation	202-203delAG del exon 4	202-203delAG del exon 4	c.255delA Homozygosis	c.255delA Homozygosis	del exon 3,4 Del exon4	c.255delA Homozygosis	del exon1 c.154delA	c.255delA C352Y exon 9
Disease duration (years)	45	30	35	33	22	14	28	10
Family History of PD	1 Sister	1 Sister	1 Sister	1 Brother	None	Grandfather	⁴ Brother/Sister	None
Late H/M MIBG ratio	1.00	1.56	1.54	1.27	1.75	1.82	1.27	2.00
Maneuver with abnormal HR & BP response	Deep breathing	None (all normal)	Deep breathing	None (all normal)	None (all normal)	None (all normal)	None (all normal)	Orthostatic Tachycardia on TTT
Result on Brief Smell test	Abnormal	Normal	Abnormal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
Scopa-Aut score	3	3	15	3	1	2	4	1
Ewing & Clarke test	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0,5

HR:Heart Rate. BP: blood pressure. Results for each autonomic test were classified as normal (0 point), borderline (0,5 point) and abnormal (1 point). Ewing's classification of autonomic failure was determined as shown below for each participant who had complied with sufficient tests: normal: all tests normal or one borderline (0-0,5 point); early: one of the HR tests abnormal or two borderlines (1 point); definite: two or more of the HR tests abnormal (2 point); severe: two or more of the HR tests abnormal plus one or both of the BP tests abnormal or both borderlines (3e5 point).

Table 2: Characteristics of Parkinson's disease in *PARK2* gene mutation carriers and in patients with idiopathic PD (iPD) at study inclusion.

	<i>PARK2</i> gene mutation carriers (n = 8)	iPD patients (n = 13)	P value
Age (years)	60.1 ± 12.8	59.2 ± 8.9	ns
Time from diagnosis (years)	27.1 ± 11.4	6.5 ± 5.1	P < 0.001
UPDRS I	2.0 ± 1.8	2.1 ± 1.8	ns
UPDRS II	10.7 ± 8.7	9.6 ± 2.7	ns
UPDRS III	28.1 ± 15.4	26.5 ± 7.5	ns
UPDRS IV	4.4 ± 3.0	3.9 ± 3.7	ns
BSIT	7.7 ± 3.2	6.0 ± 2.6	0.04
Levodopa-equivalent doses	570.5 ± 208.2	680.8 ± 459.9	ns

Results are presented as means ± standard deviations for every variable. UPDRS: Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale. BSIT: Brief Smell Identification Test. ns: no significant difference.

Table 3: Results of SCOPA-AUT, MIBG scintigraphy, noradrenergic tests and non-invasive tests of autonomic nervous system function in PD patients with and without parkin gene mutations.

	<i>PARK2</i> gene mutations (N = 8)	PD patients with no mutations (N = 13)	Normal values in our centre
SCOPA-AUT**	3.4 (4.8)	14.7 (7.2)	8.9 (5.4)
• Digestive*	1.5 (2.1)	3.6 (3.4)	
• Urinary*	1.7 (2.7)	4.2 (2.8)	
• Haemodynamics	0.1 (0.3)	0.4 (0.7)	
• Pupil	0.1 (0.3)	0.6 (0.8)	
• Thermoregulation*	0.1 (0.1)	1.8 (1.9)	
• Sexual*	0.1 (0.1)	1.8 (1.9)	
Noradrenaline Supine (pg/ml)	258.7 (127.9)	305.7 (269.8)	300e650
Standing	395.8 (195.2)	445.0 (311.0)	450e850
Vasopressin Supine*(pg/ml)	7.1 (3.9)	3.5 (4.7)	0e7.6
Standing	9.5 (7.2)	4.6 (5.5)	0e7.6
MIBG* (heart/mediastinum ratio e 4 h)	1.5 (0.3)*	1.3 (0.2)*	1.75
TILT TABLE: Blood pressure (Heart rate)			
• D systolic 3 m	−08.7 (16.7)	−3.7 (25.4)	Not available
• D diastolic 3 m	−10.8 (12.2)	−11.9 (17.4)	
Orthostatic Hypotension (n)	0	3	0
Non-invasive autonomic function tests			
• HR variability during paced breathing	1.1 (0.1)	1.1 (0.1)	1.2e1.8 (Age-dependent)
• BP Valsalva: Phase II (mmHg)	−13.4 (28.6)	−19.5 (21.9)	Not available
• BP Valsalva: Phase II late (mmHg)	9.4 (20.3)	6.6 (41.9)	Not available
• BP Valsalva: Phase IV (mmHg)	15.7 (31.2)	25.9 (15.1)	Not available
• BP changes during Handgrip test	9.2 (9.8)	8.8 (26.0)	BP changes during handgrip test: 10% increment of diastolic BP at 3 min.

Characteristics of Parkinson's disease in *PARK2* gene mutation carriers and in patients with idiopathic PD (iPD) at study inclusion. Magnitude of blood pressure (BP) changes was determined for late phase II and phase IV of the Valsalva maneuver. Values were calculated by subtracting the baseline systolic blood pressure from the systolic blood pressure during phase II or phase IV. BP changes during the handgrip test are shown as percent increment of diastolic BP at 3 min. PD e Parkinson's Disease, SCOPA-AUT- Scales for Outcomes in Parkinson's disease-autonomic, MIBG - metaiodobenzylguanidine, HR-Heart Rate. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.001.